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**Uncertainty estimation of gravity wave parameters by
Monte Carlo Simulation**

P. Preusse¹, S. Rhode¹

¹Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ), *Wilhelm-Johnen-Straße, 52428 Jülich, Germany*

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<i>Names of authors</i> P. Preusse, S. Rhode		
<i>ESA Technical Officer</i> Alex Hoffmann Division Mission Science Division Directorate Directorate of Earth Observation Programmes	<i>ESA budget heading</i>	

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Uncertainty estimation of gravity wave parameters by Monte Carlo simulation

Peter Preusse¹, Jörn Ungermann¹, and Sebastian Rhode¹

¹Institute of Climate and Energy Systems (ICE-4: Stratosphere), Forschungszentrum Jülich, Jülich, Germany

Abstract. Uncertainty estimation for wave parameters of individual gravity waves is, to the authors' knowledge, unprecedented. As the problem is highly non-linear, standard methods of a linear expansion around an optimal solution are not applicable or at least non-trivial. The problem is further complicated by the fact that an originally white detector noise is "colored" by the retrieval. The method applied in this study is therefore Monte Carlo simulation taking into account the full process of radiative transfer and retrieval. The resulting uncertainties of single-wave parameters are, for a core altitude region, well compatible to the requirements inferred from scientific applications such as ray-tracing.

Note: for technical reasons the panel specification a), b), ... is currently at the lower left

. This CAIRT technical note shall be made only available in ways that do not prevent publication in e.g. AMT

1 Introduction

Classical methods such as Fourier transform or wavelet analysis are performed on an orthogonal basis of sine and cosine functions and calculate the amplitudes for this spectral grid. Uncertainties, if provided, are then solely related to the spectral power of the individual wave components defined by this fixed spectral grid. Accordingly, wave parameters such as the wavevector do not have an uncertainty associated. However, we intuitively interpret an observed wave as having a specific horizontal and vertical wavelength and wave direction (or equivalently having a dominant wavevector). This approach is well suited for wave theory and can be used for instance to perform backtracing. The good results of GW ray-tracing (Preusse et al., 2014; Krisch et al., 2017; Strube et al., 2021; Perrett et al., 2021; Krasauskas et al., 2023; Noble et al., 2024, e.g.) are then a confirmation of this intuitive approach. The approach challenges, however, how uncertainties can be inferred in particular

1. in the presence of noise
2. for superpositions of spectrally dependent waves
3. for waves deviating in shape from perfectly plane waves

Note that (2) is related to the size of the analysis volume and important in particular when strong spatial localization of the waves is desired, either due to the physical nature of the problem or due to the limited extent of observational data sets.

The questions to be pursued are

- Are the identified waves unique and stable?
- How large is the uncertainty for a stable solution?

Figure 1. Illustration of the wave parameters defining a plane wave. In addition to the geometrical parameters wavelengths (λ_z and λ_h) and wave direction α , there is the wave amplitude ruling the minimum and maximum values indicated by color.

The approach followed in this study is based on a few-wave decomposition method (S3D) (Lehmann et al., 2012) applied to realistic data, i.e. synthetic observations from model data which resolve atmospheric GWs to a good degree. These are perturbed by superposed noise in a Monte Carlo approach and tomographic temperature retrieval and subsequent S3D applied to the individual Monte Carlo samples.

Figure 2. Overview of the processing flow from regularly sampled WACCM data to uncertainty overviews

2 Data and data flow

Data are from a WACCM run nudged up to 30km to ERA-5. No GW parametrization is used. Data are 'humped' in order to enhance the spectral contribution between 100 km and 250 km horizontal wavelength, i.e. the data are spectrally decomposed in zonal direction by an FFT, the spectra scaled in the short-wavelength range with a factor $v * \exp((z - \mu)^4 / \sigma^4)$ in the zonal wavenumber space. In this case a factor $v=2.0$ and wavenumbers of $\mu = 170$ and $\sigma = 80$ led to closer resemblance between WACCM and ECMWF data at 30 km altitude. After scaling the spectra are retransformed into spatial space. The data are then resampled onto a rectangular grid following the CAIRT orbit. To the orbit data radiative transfer, parametrized noise and retrieval are applied. S3D is applied in a k-fit / refit manner with a cascade for the k-fit and a $5 \times 5 \times 5$ point cuboid for the refit (cf. section 2.1). In the study, CAIRT-sampled data are used for reference against which the Monte Carlo samples are evaluated. The overall flow is depicted in Figure 2. The steps after applying S3D are performed via the script `main_flow_mc_evaluation.py` and detailed below.

2.1 Wave analysis with S3D

S3D is applied for wavevector determination in a cascade of three horizontal cuboid sizes of 275×450 km, 175×450 km and 125×350 km in across-track x along-track direction, where for each cuboid size 2 fits are performed. This leads in total to 6 wave components (WCs). The vertical extent of all cuboids is 11 km for the stratosphere, 13 km for the stratopause and 15 km for the mesosphere. A reliability filter of maximum wavelength 3.5 times larger than the cuboid size is applied¹. Amplitudes and phases are then refitted in a cuboid size of $125 \times 250 \times 5$ km absed on the k -vectors obtained in the cascade. In particular the reduction in vertical cuboid size is important to capture vertical gradients. GWMF is determined from the original k -vectors of the cascade and the amplitudes of the refits.

2.2 Overview over MC evaluation

An overview of the individual steps of `main_flow_mc_evaluation.py` is given in Figure 3

¹This is considered separately for horizontal and vertical direction and via a norm between the two horizontal directions (more in the S3D paper)

Figure 3. Overview of the processing flow from regularly sampled WACCM data to uncertainty overviews

2.3 Sorting wave components to the reference

As a first step, the order of WCs in the MC sample is resorted with respect to the CAIRT-sampled reference. The motivation is as follows: In cases where two similarly strong waves are superposed in the same volume, noise may lead to a different order of identification. In order to correct for this, the distance in wavenumber space between the different fit results is calculated for every pair of WC combinations. The data are resorted, if a) a pair of WCs has lower distance than the distance of the same WC between reference and MC sample and b) the difference of the pair is smaller than 0.35 of the "natural" Fourier grid. Since the grid varies for the different WC of a cascade the smaller k -threshold is used, if different cuboid sizes are compared. This is likely a reason for a higher resorting probability among pairs of same cuboid size (i.e. WC-1 and WC-2; WC-3 and WC-4; and WC-5 and WC-6, respectively). An example for a resorting statistics is shown in Figure 4. The stronger the wave and hence the lower the WC the clearer is the identification. For WC-1 almost no resorting occurs, WC-6 is more likely to be resorted than not and resorting to the next component alone is as likely as keeping the same WC. This indicates that WC-6 often only takes noise remnants in the spectral analysis, which is a consequence of rather using more WC than strictly necessary than losing relevant information by aborting the WC cascade too early. As far as dominant wave events exist in the given volume, after resorting we can expect that they are stored in the same WC for all MC samples.

Figure 4. Sorting statistics of the 6 WCs for one of the MC samples resorted to the sampled data.

Table 1. Categories of selection and selection criteria

category name	selection criteria
all	selection only for altitude, track and WC
selected	maximum horizontal and vertical wavelength; minimum amplitude
unambiguous	number of “same waves” larger than threshold
selected and unambiguous	both criteria above

2.4 Statistical evaluation: general distributions

Not every fit is reliable, which will be discussed for the statistical evaluation below. There are two main reasons why a fit is not reliable: a) the wavelength is very long and hence the χ^2 minimum very close to the origin in spectral space. As we also will see below, this leads to a very large wavelength uncertainty as well as loss of direction information. b) the amplitude is small compared to the noise and other disturbances, so in an MC experiment it cannot be safely identified. Therefore the following categories are introduced, as listed in table 1.

The selection criteria are $\lambda_h < 3000$ km; $\lambda_z < 40$ km; $T_{amp} > 0.1K$. This selection is evaluated on the reference and then applied to all MC samples, i.e. if a wave event (specified by its location and WC) is exceeding the selection criteria in the reference it is removed entirely from later evaluation. The criteria for the reproduction of the “same wave” are individually applied to the considered variables and relatively loosely defined as 50% for vertical and horizontal wavelength and 50° for wave direction. A threshold of at least 8 MC-samples, i.e. 50% of all MC experiments performed, then selects waves where a dominant wave can be unambiguously identified. Varying the threshold number of reproduced samples would allow a trade between the number of still-“good” events and the quality of the reproduction. As for wavelength criteria, wave events which cannot be unambiguously identified are completely removed (all MC samples).

Figures 5 and 6 show the distributions of MC-samples for 35 km – an altitude where CAIRT possesses a good amplitude/noise ratio (cf. section 5). The along-orbit distributions show that spread is not homogeneous but clusters in recurring regions of larger spread (likely dependent on latitude). For the first wave component, the reference from orbit-sampled data without retrieval is identified in almost all MC samples. Wave component 4 fits the residual after removing three leading WCs. That given, it is rather remarkable that 14% of the analyzed cuboids identify the same wave in all 16 MC samples and 50% in more than 8 MC samples. Also the peak is rather sharp around 0° indicating that for most MC samples the identified wave direction is close to the reference value. It is interesting though, that the wave events which could not be clearly defined form a side-peak at $\pm 90^\circ$ difference to the reference. Comparing amplitude-weighted and number distribution, it becomes evident that this is often due to low amplitude waves or, in fact, noise.

2.5 Statistical evaluation: Calculation of value and uncertainty

Even a limited volume such as an S3D analysis cuboid spans a substantial spectral space allowing for many independent spectral solutions. This resembles somewhat an egg carton where the dimples are the minima in χ^2 space taking the individual eggs, i.e. wave solutions. What we are interested in, is how much the shape of one considered dimple is altered by the superposition with noise or with the tails from other dimples (i.e. other wave solutions). This will tell us how precise a given wave solution can be determined. We here want to disregard whether the algorithm may throw us to a completely different solution. (The sorting will have reduced, but not eliminated such mismatches. In particular, once the main components are removed, noise likely causes a larger number of dimples with comparable depth. These are spurious waves, i.e. cannot be interpreted in terms

Figure 5. Distribution of all wave events and all MC samples for WC 1 for the propagation direction for a) all analysis locations along the center track. The number of the MC sample is color coded, b) percentage of events where MC samples match the reference, c) distribution over all locations and MC-samples for the amplitude and d) same, but for the number

of GWs). Therefore, the “*same wave*” criteria of 50% for vertical and horizontal wavelength and 50° for wave direction are applied before calculating the standard deviations and means. Again, wave events which do match in less than 50% of the cases are not considered meaningful.²

Resulting distributions of the standard deviation of the wave direction over all wave events (all geographical locations) for WC-1 (high likelihood for unambiguous wave identification) and WC-4 (mixture of noise and real waves) are shown in Figure 7. For WC-1 the distribution is well-peaked and narrow, for WC-4 the distribution rather broad. In both cases, the width is substantially smaller than the cutting criterion, i.e. the criterion does not bias the width of a given χ^2 minimum (a given dimple). It is also evident that the “unambiguous” criterion removes about 50% of the cases for WC-4.

An overview of the standard deviations of (relative) differences for the various variables for WC-1 is given in Figure 8. The leanest distributions are for vertical wavelength and direction, which are also the variables most important for launching ray-traces. The broadest distributions are for amplitude and GWMF. In no case the distributions are limited by the cutting thresholds. (Cutting criteria for amplitude and GWMF are 0.8.)

²Where to set the threshold may depend on the application. For statistical evaluations such as zonal mean GWMF distributions it likely is beneficial to risk some minor misidentifications and keep a good representation of all analyzed locations and all parts of the GW spectrum. For ray-tracing experiments one may, conversely, rather wish to keep only such cases which are truly unambiguously identified.

Figure 6. Same as Figure 5 but for WC4

Figure 7. Standard deviations for WC1 and WC4 and different degrees of selection.

Figure 8. Distributions of standard deviations of differences from the reference for WC-1 for all wave events, for a) wave direction b) amplitude c) vertical wavelength and d) horizontal wavelength. Absolute difference for direction (a); relative difference for all other variables ((b) to (e)). Absolute GW momentum flux (panel e) is inferred for the individual events and the standard deviation of these calculated.

3 Spectral dependency of uncertainty

The resulting uncertainty varies with horizontal and vertical wavelength as shown in Figure 9. Reasons may be the width and the position of the χ^2 minimum in spectral space, how close the real world is to the assumption of a plane wave and the ratio between amplitude and noise (or in our picture the depth of the dimple). In the following we offer some interpretations which may lead to the spectral dependencies seen in Figure 9.

At 35 km altitude the maximum of the amplitude spectrum is a broad maximum around 10 km vertical wavelength and 1000 km horizontal wavelength. Amplitude to noise ratio is hence highest at such wavelengths and relative noise contributions increase for, in particular, short and long vertical wavelength. Also, when many wave cycles are contained in the fitting cuboid, the plane-wave assumption is less likely to be matched. Again that effect is expected to be more likely violated in the vertical where refraction by the background wind induces strong vertical wavelength changes even over the altitude range of a cuboid. When the wavelength is larger than the cuboid extent, the width of the χ^2 minimum becomes large relative to the wavelength.³ Accordingly, we can understand the distributions as follows:

a) vertical wavelength is best fitted where amplitudes are high. Longer horizontal wavelengths are more easily described by plane waves.

b) horizontal wavelength works better for medium vertical wavelength (plane wave assumption). As the width of the χ^2 minimum is constant in k , the relative accuracy of horizontal wavelength is higher for shorter horizontal wavelength.

c) direction is defined via the direction of the wavevector, i.e. directly in wave space (cf. Figure 1. At a given width of the χ^2 minimum the direction is hence best defined at large k values far from the center. For very long horizontal wavelength the solution is close to the origin at and would, at some point, lose direction information completely.

d) amplitude Mainly: larger amplitudes lead to lower relative uncertainties and the distribution becomes the inverse of the amplitude spectra as generated by the atmospheric model (largest amplitudes around 10km vertical and 1000km horizontal wavelength).

e) GWMF is strongest influenced by amplitude (dependence of \hat{T}^2), but influence of horizontal-wavelength uncertainty partly compensates the shape and accordingly the overall uncertainty is quite flat.

³The width is constant in k-space, relatively large for small k, and wavelength is the inverse of k.

Figure 9. Spectra of inferred uncertainty for the different variables for WC-1 and 35 km altitude.

4 Wave component composition of reliable spectral contributions

The estimated uncertainty for the 6 WCs are shown in Figure 10. As defined above, the cuboid cascade uses three horizontal cuboid sizes of 275x450 km, 175x450 km and 125x350 km in across-track x along-track direction. The smaller cuboid sizes for WC-3, WC-4 and WC-5, WC-6, respectively, lead to shorter horizontal cut-off wavelengths at the long-horizontal-wavelength edge. Though the Nyquist wavelength is 50 km in across-track direction in all cases, in practice a smaller horizontal cuboid dimension leads also to a populated area extending towards shorter horizontal wavelengths. The area of highest amplitude wave events around 1000 km horizontal wavelength and 10 km vertical wavelength is mostly represented by WC-1 and WC-2. WC-6 is then mainly taking the fringes of the wave space. As amplitudes decrease at higher WC and the larger WC are probably noise dominated, the uncertainty becomes larger.

Figure 10. Overview of uncertainty estimates for different WC, with upper row 275x450 km cuboid size in across-track x along-track direction, middle row 175x450 km and lower row 125x350 km

Figure 11. Zonal mean uncertainty of unambiguous events for wavelengths, direction, amplitude and GWMF.

5 Spatial dependency of uncertainty

Height-latitude cross sections of uncertainty for WC1 are shown in Figure 11. Uncertainties are smallest for mid and upper stratospheric altitudes. At higher altitudes (>60 km) the ratio between infrared radiance and detector noise decreases strongly. At these altitudes the uncertainty of the valid wave events increases, but also the number of reliable values decreases. For lower altitudes a main reason for increased uncertainty is the background removal which cuts at zonal wavenumber 7 (ZWN7). Below 25 km altitude this does not allow for a proper separation from synoptic scale Rossby waves (Strube et al., 2020) with increasing artifacts at lower altitudes. This biases the wavelength distributions towards longer horizontal wavelengths. A way out might be using assimilation data for background removal. The investigated WACCM-X data resolve GWs properly only for horizontal wavelengths longer than 200 km. The presence of shorter waves, which in reality are more abundant than in the WACCM-X simulations, would also alleviate this problem. This is further discussed below in Section 5.1.

Figure 12 shows the average number of identifications in the Monte Carlo experiment for the different wave components. For WC-1 almost all Monte Carlo samples identify the reference wave, at least below 65km. Above this altitude noise increases and the number of correct identifications decreases. For the larger WC, the number generally decreases and starting with WC-4 the average number of correct identifications is less than half of the total number of Monte Carlo samples.

The average number of identifications almost directly maps to the fraction of reliably identifiable waves shown in Fig. 13. WC-1 to WC-3 quite often find the same waves in a larger number of samples, indicating that these WCs are representing in general real waves. The picture changes above 65km where the numbers drop drastically due to the increasing instrument noise. Thus, while even at higher altitudes there are some stronger wave events which can be well identified beyond the noise level, this is not the case for the majority of the fitting volumes. As a consequence, for calculating zonal mean GWMF one has now the choice between two evils: a) apply only the cuboid-size selection i.e. average over all fits with reasonable wavelengths in comparison to the cuboid extent and thus average mainly over noise or b) select, in addition, only those waves which can be identified unambiguously and then average over a few remaining waves only, which then, however, is not longer representative. Fig. 14 discussed in Section 5.1 chooses option a) and we see that the CAIRT-observed GWMF deviates from the model reference strongly above 65 km.

5.1 Error assessment by comparing to GWMF based on model winds

The zonal mean GWMF error assessment of Fig. 14 does take into account only filtering due to cuboid size, but not due to uniqueness. Above 65km then still many values are taken into account, but with a high noise level. Accordingly, values inferred via S3D wave analysis differ largely from the reference calculated from the model winds. For the stratosphere,

Figure 12. Average number of those wave fits which reproduce the fit result from the reference data, i.e. from the S3d results of orbit-sampled data.

ECMWF analysis data are shown in the profile plots as well. ECMWF contains GWs down to 100 km horizontal wavelength,

Figure 13. Zonal mean fraction of unambiguous and reliable identifications: Values of 1 indicates that for all cuboids in the respective bin at least 50% of the Monte Carlo samples find the reference wave, values of 0 that the original wave is never found in at least 50% of the samples.

i.e. substantially shorter wavelengths than the WACCM data. This makes the data less sensitive to the ZWN7 limit of the background removal and agreement between S3D results (even for retrievals)⁴ and wind-derived data is much higher.

⁴There should be the opposite effect that radiative transfer suppresses short horizontal wavelengths at least in along-track direction. Obviously this effect is much less important than the background removal.

Figure 14. Zonal mean error analysis comparing analysed GWMF derived from S3D analysis of temperatures (b, c) with a reference from winds on the full model grid (c). The S3D zonal means include all reliable waves (reliable according to wavelength/cuboid-size criteria) for all WC. For a more quantitative comparisons, profiles are extracted from panels a) to c) and shown for the NH polar vortex in d) and the SH convection regions in e). Panel f) compares these deviations with a threshold of 30% and shows the result in terms of a traffic light plot.

6 Summary and Outlook

To our knowledge so far no uncertainty estimates for the parameters of individual GWs exist. This study develops a Monte Carlo method to estimate uncertainties for gravity wave parameters inferred from 3D observational data. It is here applied to synthetic CAIRT observations generated from WACCM-X data, which resolve GWs down to horizontal scales of ~ 200 km. In a core altitude region of 25km to 60km, CAIRT data can be analyzed with high confidence. The first wave component (WC-1) can almost always be inferred trustworthy. The number of safe wave identifications decreases for higher wave components and is very low for WC-5 and WC-6, indicating that these WC in the majority of cases are representing noise or deviations from the plane-wave assumption. At altitudes > 65 km noise dominates, at altitudes < 25 km the background removal up to ZWN 7 is insufficient.

Radiative transfer and retrieval color the noise. While limb-sounder retrievals have a tendency to generate a retrieval oscillation in the vertical (blue noise), this is counteracted by a retrieval regularization which then would redden the noise.

PP: My expectations and not-followed up loose observations: The effects of differently colored noise are as follows

- blue noise just creates a χ^2 rim of low values at the cuboid edges in spectral space. It can well be suppressed by the penalty function but is also the reason that WC5 and WC6 are in most cases garbage collectors
- strong retrieval regularization actually creates kind of a χ^2 minimum at medium wavelengths. My recollection, but really never followed up
- reddish noise should create a background in χ^2 with a slope. I would expect some systematic shifts of the determined wave parameters in accordance with this slope. To be investigated with idealized experiments.

The results shown in this study compare Monte Carlo samples against an unperturbed analysis result, which is taken for a reference truth. For real observations we do not have such a reference truth. As a potential solution, a median approach is already implemented. In order to prepare for real data, which start from an observation including noise, we would need to mimic this process in a simulation. This would base on a “parent” sample including simulated noise (representative of the real

observation) and further-perturbed “child” implementations of the MC experiment which superimpose noise on the “parent” experiment rather than on the ideal situation.

MC simulations are costly. The hope hence is that better understanding the influence of noise on the χ^2 distribution would allow a more direct (e.g. parametrized) method to infer uncertainties from the depth of the χ^2 minima (“dimples”) and the height of the noise in spectral space.

Specifically suggested are the following steps:

- investigate the median implementation using simulated CAIRT data and a "parent"-“child” approach
- understand better how noise influences the χ^2 distributions
- what does this mean for (almost) noise-free model data which, however,
 - contain a superposition of several waves in every volume
 - contain waves which deviate from plane waves
- application to real data such as AIRS and IASI, MATS and in future H-FORT

7 Note on median for reference generation

In principle, the external reference (CAIRT-sampled data) can be replaced by a median. This would also allow a MC analysis if the truth is not known (i.e. real observation data). In the current implementation, however, resorting is always to a truth, i.e. for real data one would need to have a, potentially iterative, separate step of reference wave parameter generation.

. This work was performed for CAIRT uncertainty estimation in the frame of the CAIRT PerReC study.

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